

Sampling: comparison of means**Options**

Type I error (Alpha,Significance):	0.05
Type II error (Beta, 1-Power):	0.20

Data

Difference of means	5
Standard deviation in group 1	8.9
Standard deviation in group 2	12.4

Result

Number of cases required in Group 1:	74
Number of cases required in Group 2:	74
Total sample size (both groups together):	148

Table

		Type I Error - Alpha			
		0.20	0.10	0.05	0.01
Type II Error - Beta	0.20	43 + 43	59 + 59	74 + 74	110 + 110
	0.10	62 + 62	81 + 81	99 + 99	140 + 140
	0.05	81 + 81	102 + 102	122 + 122	167 + 167
	0.01	122 + 122	148 + 148	172 + 172	225 + 225